

TEACHER CHARACTER AND EDUCATION QUALITY IN SOUTH SULAWESI: A PUBLIC POLICY AND SOCIOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE

Tatang Sudrajat¹, Andi Cahaya², Irmawati³, M. Awaluddin⁴

Sangga Buana University¹, Bandung,

Cahaya Prima University^{2, 3, 4}, Bone

id.tatangsudrajat@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The challenges and problems to realize quality education are getting bigger. Strengthening the character of students through professional and characterful teachers will support quality education. All levels of government, including in South Sulawesi, are committed to the emergence of civilized teachers. Governor Regulation (Pergub) Number 145 of 2017 concerning Teacher Manners and several other state and government regulations are public policies that are oriented towards the ethical, moral and character values of teachers as educators. This study aims to analyze the profile, context, and substance of the policy as well as the sociological dimensions in the Pergub and various other government regulations.

This study uses normative legal methods and literature studies, by examining the substance of government regulations and analyzing various relevant documents. The results of the study indicate that Pergub Number 145 of 2017 is a public policy on character education. Hierarchically, there are several government policies as references, including Presidential Regulation Number 87 of 2017, Regulation of the Minister of National Education Number 23 of 2015 and South Sulawesi Provincial Regulation Number 2 of 2016. There are several policy aspects in the Pergub, namely policy hierarchy, policy objectives, policy substance, policy implementers, policy targets, details of policy activities, and policy resources. Several regional officials, school leaders, teachers and community members are policy actors. In addition, there are several sociological aspects regulated in the Pergub. The emergence of civilized students through civilized teachers is a policy issue. The provincial government, DPRD, educational organizations and institutions outside the government related to the issue of character education are policy institutions. The public's hope for better quality education through civilized teachers and students is a policy environment. There are several policy substances in the gubernatorial regulation that need to be improved.

Keywords: teacher character, policy, quality of education, sociological.

INTRODUCTION

The importance of education has been a concern of the nation's founders since its inception, as evident in the provisions of the nation's constitution. Education is believed to be the fundamental capital for Indonesia to emerge as a superior nation on earth. In other words, quality education will be a major contributor to the birth of a generation that will continue the struggle to achieve the ideals of independence. According to Wahyudi, the better the quality of a country's education, the more it will impact the nation's progress (2022:25).

Therefore, the presence of teachers as educators at the elementary to secondary levels is a strategic and determining factor in achieving quality education. This will undoubtedly be supported by the character of teachers as educators and the character of students, who reflect attitudes and behaviors that uphold ethical and moral values. Students with character are, among other things, the product of the attitudes and behavior of teachers with character, as role models remain an important part of social interaction. Paternalistic culture remains dominant in various levels of Indonesian society, making the role model of teachers crucial in developing students with character.

Generally, in societal discussions, this character is closely related to the integrity of teachers and students as human beings, characterized by, among other things, politeness, honesty, loyalty, sincerity, commitment, and devotion. In other words, it relates to the character of the Indonesian people, which collectively constitutes the character of the nation. Therefore, in national life, human character significantly determines the quality of the nation, including in state governance and national development. According to Lickona, character consists of operative values and values in action. Thus conceived, character has three interrelated components: moral knowing, moral feeling, and moral behavior. Good character consists of knowing the good, desiring the good, and doing the good—habits of the mind, habits of the heart, and habits of action (1992:51). Moral values evident in human attitudes and behavior are crucial for developing the nation's character as a whole.

In this regard, character education is crucial and strategic, receiving careful attention from the government as mandated by the constitution. National intelligence, as one of the goals of the nation's founding, is certainly not merely intellectual intelligence. National character is considered a crucial determinant of the nation's future progress. The government has established policies, including Presidential Regulation (Perpres) Number 87 of 2017 concerning Strengthening Character Education. Furthermore, as an elaboration of Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, each regional government has also issued regional

policies in the form of regional regulations and regional head regulations concerning the implementation of education. One of the substantive policies stipulated within these regulations concerns character education.

In South Sulawesi Province, Governor Regulation Number 145 of 2017 concerning Teacher Etiquette was issued, which substantively emphasizes the importance of ethics, morals, integrity, and character in the educational process. As an integral part of the national governance system, this naturally has a hierarchical relationship with various state regulations and higher-level governments. Various state/government regulations regarding character education constitute public policy. According to Gerston, public policy is the combination of basic decisions, commitments, and actions made by those who hold or influence government positions of authority (2010:7). In other words, it can be said that this is part of education policy, or public policy that falls within the realm of education. This aligns with Parsons's argument that some of the key areas of public policy include health, transportation, education, and environmental and social policy (1997:31). One substantive area of this public policy is education, particularly character education.

This gubernatorial regulation constitutes public policy because it was enacted by the Governor of South Sulawesi, acting as a state official to address public concerns regarding the morality of the younger generation, including students in general. Within this framework, conceptually, evaluative analysis is necessary to refine all government regulations, especially after the policies are implemented. Wollmann defines policy evaluation as an analytical tool and procedure intended to accomplish two things. First, it investigates policy programs to obtain all information related to assessing their performance, both process and outcome. Second, evaluation, as a stage in the policy cycle, generally refers to reporting this information back to the policymaking process (Fischer et al., 2015:554). According to Dunn, policy evaluation is a policy analytic procedure used to produce information about the performance of policies in satisfying the needs, values, and opportunities that constitute a "problem." (1981:339).

This research aims to analyze and evaluate the substance of state and government regulations as public policy, which constitutes one element of the Policy System, and to examine the substance of these policies from a sociological perspective. These government regulations include Governor Regulation Number 145 of 2017, as well as all laws and regulations pertaining to character education established by policymakers at various levels of government.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research combines normative juridical methods with policy evaluation, literature review, and documentation. This research, based on its explanatory level, is descriptive research, one form of which is library and documentary research. The normative juridical method is a type of research commonly used in legal science, or normative legal research, or library law, which is conducted through the examination of library materials or secondary data alone. The focus of the study is on all forms of information documented in regulations, thus commonly known as document analysis or content analysis.

The study focused specifically on South Sulawesi Gubernatorial Regulation No. 145 of 2017 and South Sulawesi Regional Regulation No. 2 of 2016. Furthermore, all state and government regulations related to character education were reviewed, including Law No. 20 of 2003, Presidential Regulation No. 87 of 2017, Minister of Education and Culture Regulation No. 23 of 2015 concerning the Development of Character, and Minister of Education and Culture Regulation No. 20 of 2018 concerning Strengthening Character Education in Formal Education Units. Furthermore, various sources were reviewed, including books, journals, proceedings, research reports, and other literature relevant to the research objectives.

Documentation data collection techniques were conducted by exploring and compiling several laws and regulations, both directly and indirectly related to the existence of regulations regarding Teacher Etiquette and character education in general. Various non-human data sources, such as documents, photographs, and statistical materials, can be considered as sources that are expected to provide adequate information in accordance with the research objectives. All of these documents relate to the substance of the Teacher Manners policy or program in South Sulawesi. The technique used to analyze secondary data is content analysis, which is used to obtain various data and information regarding all forms of communication delivered in symbolic form, including letters, regulations, and laws. All of this data is classified, reviewed, interpreted, and then conclusions are drawn.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile, Hierarchy, and Policy Context

Legally, the policy on teacher conduct in South Sulawesi Province is inseparable from the national education policy, namely Law Number 20 of 2003. This state regulation, enacted on July 8, 2003, consists of 77 articles, including the abolition of Law Number 2 of 1989 concerning the National Education System. Its connection to character education is evident, among other things, in Article 1, number 1, concerning the definition of education, Article 3 concerning the function of national education,

and Article 4 Paragraph (1) concerning the principles of education implementation. Hierarchically, this law was issued based on five articles of the 1945 Constitution, and adapting Bromley's theory on the hierarchy of public policy, the regulation, which was established as a joint product between the Indonesian House of Representatives (DPR RI) as the legislative body and the President of the Republic of Indonesia, is at the policy level (1989:32-33).

Presidential Regulation Number 87 of 2017 was enacted on September 6, 2017, and consists of 18 articles. The relationship of this presidential regulation to character education is illustrated, among other things, by the title of the presidential regulation and the consideration in letter b, which states that strengthening character education is necessary to realize a cultured nation. In terms of policy hierarchy, Article 13 Paragraph (5) of the presidential regulation states, among other things, that each regional government is responsible for formulating policies and implementing action plans in accordance with its authority.

Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 23 of 2015 consisting of 9 Articles was stipulated on July 13, 2015 as a replacement for Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 21 of 2015. The issuance of this regulation is based on Law Number 20 of 2003 and Government Regulation Number 17 of 2003. The context with character education is seen in the consideration of letter c that character education should be a joint movement involving the government, regional government, community, and/or parents. Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 20 of 2018 consisting of 15 articles was stipulated on June 7, 2018, which is the realization of the provisions of Article 14 of Presidential Regulation Number 87 of 2017. Hierarchically, this Minister of Education and Culture Regulation is stipulated based on Law Number 20 of 2003, Government Regulation Number 19 of 2005, and Government Regulation Number 17 of 2010. The context with character education is clearly visible as stated in the title of this Minister of Education and Culture Regulation. From a public policy perspective, Government Regulation No. 19 of 2005, Government Regulation No. 17 of 2010, Presidential Regulation No. 87 of 2017, and Ministerial Regulation No. 20 of 2018, in relation to government hierarchy, refer to Bromley's opinion, and can be placed at the organizational level (1989:32-33). This aligns with Gerston's view that one component of public policy is the level of government that addresses issues (2010:8).

South Sulawesi Provincial Regulation Number 2 of 2016, enacted on March 17, 2016, consists of 70 articles that replace Regional Regulation Number 4 of 2009 concerning the Provision of Free Education in South Sulawesi Province. Hierarchically, the issuance of this regional regulation is based on, among others, Law

Number 20 of 2003, Law Number 14 of 2005, Law Number 23 of 2014, Government Regulation Number 19 of 2005, Government Regulation Number 74 of 2008, and Government Regulation Number 17 of 2010. Its context with character education is stated in Article 3 Paragraph (1) letter a and Article 6 letter b, which relate to exemplary behavior.

South Sulawesi Governor Regulation Number 145 of 2017, which was stipulated on September 29, 2017, consists of 11 articles and is the realization of the provisions of Article 12 paragraph (2) letter d of Presidential Regulation Number 87 of 2017 and Article 6 letter d of Regional Regulation Number 2 of 2016. Hierarchically, the issuance of this regulation is based on, among others, Law Number 20 of 2003, PP Number 19 of 2005, PP Number 17 of 2010, Presidential Regulation Number 87 of 2017, Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 79 of 2014, and Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 23 of 2015. The context with character education is very clear as stated in the title of this governor regulation. From a public policy perspective, the existence of two regional policies in South Sulawesi Province, Regional Regulation No. 2 of 2016 and Governor Regulation No. 145 of 2017, using Bromley's opinion regarding the policy hierarchy, is at the operational level (1989, 32-33). This is because the education policy regarding teacher etiquette is the lowest level within the policy system framework, with the governor as the actor who establishes the policy.

Teacher Character Within the Policy System Framework

The South Sulawesi Provincial Government's attention to the importance of student character, which is expected to be developed through the practice of teacher etiquette, through the issuance of Governor Regulation No. 145 of 2017, is a concrete manifestation of public policy in the field of education. To gain a comprehensive understanding of public policy, particularly regarding teacher etiquette policy within the framework of character education in South Sulawesi, it must be viewed from various categories, which, according to Anderson, include policy demands, policy decisions, and policy statements (1978, 4-5). Policy demands are revealed in the form of various demands, complaints, opinions, aspirations, and even protests from citizens regarding the emergence of various behaviors that deviate from social norms in the world of education. Various political institutions and infrastructures in South Sulawesi have become effective means of bridging public interests with policymakers in the education sector. This is especially true with the increasing number of media or digital platforms used by the public to convey their hopes to the government. The substance of policy demands in public policy analysis includes a component of public policy that Gerston calls issues that appear on the public agenda (2010:8).

In other words, this policy was not established due to sporadic or reactionary thoughts and actions, but rather as a response by government institutions and officials, representing the state, to the problems faced by the community. In their position as public servants, they are required to be responsive to environmental dynamics, such as public concerns regarding the unethical, immoral, and normative attitudes and behaviors of some students. From a public policy perspective, the hopes, aspirations, demands, and even protests from the community to policymakers, which Anderson calls policy demands, constitute one category of public policy. The societal conditions that convey these hopes and aspirations to government officials are referred to, from a public policy perspective, as the policy environment. According to Dunn, this policy environment is the specific context in which events surrounding a policy issue occur, influence, and are in turn influenced by policy stakeholders and public policies (1981:47).

Policy decisions regarding these two regional policies in South Sulawesi Province take place within the regional government institutions authorized to establish regional regulations and gubernatorial regulations. In accordance with applicable provisions, including Law Number 23 of 2014, the policy decision to issue Regional Regulation Number 2 of 2016 was made through a collaboration between the South Sulawesi Provincial DPRD (Regional People's Representative Council) and the Governor of South Sulawesi. Governor Regulation Number 145 of 2017 came into effect upon its enactment by the governor, pursuant to his authority as head of the province. Regional officials in the Provincial DPRD, as well as the governor and all regional apparatus directly related to this regulation, constitute policy actors within the political superstructure. According to Ramesh and Howlett, these policy actors are referred to as elected officials. Policy subsystems are forums where actors discuss policy issues and engage in persuasion and bargaining in pursuit of their interests (1995:51).

Policy statements are the formal manifestation or expression of public policy after a lengthy political process, thus establishing a solid legal standing within the framework of the rule of law. Anderson argues that public policy, at least in its positive form, is based on law and is authoritative (1978:4). According to another public policy expert, Dye, one model in the study of public policymaking is the institutional model. This means that public policy is the product of government institutions, whose characteristics include legitimacy and authoritativeness (1987:24). Within the framework of a state governed by the rule of law and a democracy, this provides a solid foundation for the implementation of social welfare, including the development of educators and students with morals, ethics, and integrity.

In the reality of government and social life, it is clear that every program or policy established by the government will elicit responses from various components of society as part of the political infrastructure. This response begins even at the earliest stage, when the policy idea is introduced to the public through various communication media. The form of this public response varies, according to individual interests and perspectives, including those who express firm rejection, acceptance with reservations, or complete acceptance. In South Sulawesi, components of the political infrastructure include teacher associations, education observers, community organizations on education, educational community organizations, and the mass media.

This then serves as a reference for policymakers in legislative or executive institutions, which are part of the political superstructure, to further refine it as part of their duties and authority as mandated by the constitution and laws and regulations. Regarding education policy regarding teacher etiquette in South Sulawesi, the governor, Education Department officials, teachers, heads of educational units, education observers, education activists, and other parties involved in education are part of what Dunn calls policy stakeholders. He defines these as individuals or groups who have an interest in policies because they affect and are affected by given decisions (1981:47).

This interdependent relationship between public policy, the policy environment, and policy stakeholders constitutes a single entity that Dunn conceptually calls "The Policy System," the overall institutional pattern within which policies are made (1981:46). This means that the South Sulawesi government's policy on teacher etiquette will influence and be influenced by two other elements in the policy system: policy stakeholders and the policy environment. As an illustration, when this policy is successfully implemented, it will have a positive impact on the policy environment. This will also have a positive impact on policy stakeholders, such as improving the government's reputation among the public, which is considered successful with its character education and teacher ethics policies. Another public policy expert, Dye, states that the Policy System consists of three elements: public policy, political system, and social and economic conditions (1987:12).

The Substance of the Teacher Character Policy

From a public policy perspective, the relevance of the South Sulawesi Provincial Government's policy, in the form of Gubernurial Regulation No. 145 of 2017 concerning Teacher Etiquette, is inseparable from the national policy on character education contained in the National Education System Law. This character education is strongly relevant to state policy as stipulated in Law No. 20 of 2003. Substantively, this relevance is described in provisions regarding the definition, basis, function,

objectives, and principles of national education. The formulation of national education is stipulated in Article 1, number 2, namely, education based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, rooted in religious values and Indonesian national culture, and responsive to the demands of changing times. The explicit inclusion of religious and national cultural values as the foundation of education demonstrates the seriousness and commitment of policymakers to these two aspects in character formation.

The foundation of national education, as stated in Article 2, is Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia. This is also explicitly related to the source of national character, specifically the five fundamental values of the five Pancasila principles as the philosophical foundation, as well as the essential values concisely and comprehensively contained in the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution. The function of national education, as stated in Article 3, is to develop capabilities and shape the character and civilization of a dignified nation in order to enlighten the nation's life. This also clearly and explicitly demonstrates its relevance to the national character, which is intended to be built and developed through national education.

As stated in Article 3, the goal of national education is to develop the potential of students to become individuals who believe in and fear God Almighty, possess noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become democratic and responsible citizens. These nine characteristics of Indonesians as students that are to be developed constitute the nation's character. Education is organized based on several principles stated in Article 4, including that education is conducted democratically, fairly, and non-discriminatory, upholding human rights, religious values, cultural values, and national diversity. This also explicitly emphasizes the importance of character, which must be upheld in the implementation of education.

Furthermore, in the context of national development, the importance of national character is also mentioned in Law Number 17 of 2007 concerning the Long-Term Development Plan 2005-2025. Appendix IV.1 of the Long-Term Development Directions for 2005-2025 states, among other things, that the development and strengthening of national identity are aimed at realizing a national character and social system that is rooted, unique, modern, and superior. This is understandable, as national development must be implemented not only through people-oriented development but also through people-centered development. Developing the education sector through character education is fundamental to the future of the nation and state. Veronica and Febrina Dafit argue that character education is crucial because

it will anticipate the possibility of character depletion in the future for the nation's successors (2022:332).

Given the importance of national character as outlined in these two laws, Presidential Regulation Number 87 of 2017 was issued. The Presidential Regulation's considerations state that strengthening character education is necessary to realize a cultured nation through strengthening the values of religiousness, honesty, tolerance, discipline, hard work, creativity, independence, democracy, curiosity, national spirit, love of the homeland, appreciation of achievement, communication, peace, reading, environmental awareness, social awareness, and responsibility. One of the objectives of strengthening character education, as stated in Article 2, is to develop and equip students as Indonesia's golden generation in 2045 with the spirit of Pancasila and sound character education to face the dynamics of change in the future.

As a follow-up to the Presidential Decree, the Minister of Education and Culture issued Ministerial Regulation Number 20 of 2018. Article 2, paragraph (1), states that strengthening character education is implemented by implementing Pancasila values in character education, particularly those encompassing religious values, honesty, tolerance, discipline, hard work, creativity, independence, democracy, curiosity, national spirit, love of the homeland, appreciation of achievement, communication, love of peace, love of reading, environmental awareness, social awareness, and responsibility. Article 2, paragraph (2) states that values are the embodiment of five interrelated core values: religiosity, nationalism, independence, mutual cooperation, and integrity, which are integrated into the curriculum.

In South Sulawesi Province, character education is enshrined in a policy called Teacher Etiquette, which, as stated in Article 1, Number 7 of Governor Regulation Number 145 of 2017, is a standard of politeness, behavior, and refinement that underpins teachers' beliefs in thinking and behaving. The purpose of establishing teacher etiquette, as stated in Article 2, Paragraph (2), is crucial: encouraging the emergence of a shared vision for teachers regarding behavior and commitment, guiding teachers' professional actions in carrying out their duties, and encouraging the formation and strengthening of students' character through teacher etiquette. This aligns with Anderson's view that one of the characteristics of public policy is purposive or goal-oriented action rather than random or chance behavior is our concern (1978:3).

Article 3, Paragraph (3), states that the Education Office establishes a monitoring and evaluation team for the implementation of teacher etiquette in educational units, and Article 4, Paragraph (1) states that every teacher implements teacher etiquette. The regulation of these two things from a public policy perspective is important, because as stated by experts, one of the stages in the public policy process

is implementation (Anderson, 1978:92, Dunn, 1981:60, Howlett and M. Ramesh, 1995:153). On the other hand, in addition to teachers and heads of educational units, there are also supervisors mentioned in Article 4 Paragraph (4) who have an obligation to assist in the implementation of teacher etiquette in each educational unit. From a public policy perspective, teachers, heads of educational units, supervisors and other parties involved and interested in the policy of teacher etiquette and character education are policy actors, which according to Howlett and M. Ramesh the term actor includes both state and societal actors, some of which are intimately involved in the policy process while others are only marginally so (1995:51).

From a public policy perspective, the presence of various state regulations in the form of laws, as well as executive policies at the national and regional levels in the form of government regulations, presidential regulations, ministerial regulations, provincial regulations, and gubernatorial regulations, all of which concern or are related to character education, clearly demonstrate a policy hierarchy aligned with levels of government authority. At the most operational level, all of these laws and regulations are followed up by school principals, as heads of educational units, in accordance with their respective characteristics.

Both regional policies, as products of the democratic process, are inseparable from the expectation of improvement through evaluation, including regarding their substance. From a public policy and education policy perspective, the evaluation stage is a crucial aspect for the creation of an effective educational policy or program. This aligns with Anderson's assertion that evaluation is concerned with the estimation, assessment, or appraisal of policy, including its content, implementation, and effects (1978:151). Conducting evaluation is crucial for the future sustainability of the policy or program. This is in line with what Nachmias stated that policy evaluation as the objective systematic, empirical examination of the effects ongoing policies and public programs have on their targets in terms of the goals they are intended to achieve (Howlett and Ramesh, 1995: 169).

Sociological Dimensions of Teacher Character Policy

From a sociological perspective, the issuance of Gubernatorial Regulation No. 145 of 2017, enacted based on Regional Regulation No. 2 of 2016, represents one form of the social system's function: integration. This function, as introduced by Talcott Parsons, is implemented by the legal subsystem by maintaining procedures and integration between components with differing opinions, perspectives, and moral frameworks to foster social solidarity (Narwoko, J. Dwi, and Bagong Suyanto (eds.), 2004:76). This regional policy has impacted forms of social interaction within society, particularly within the educational community at the elementary and secondary

levels. This is illustrated by the purpose of establishing teacher morality, as stated in Article 2 of Gubernatorial Regulation No. 145 of 2017: to encourage the emergence of a shared vision of teacher behavior and commitment, guide teachers' professional actions in carrying out their duties, and encourage the formation and strengthening of student character through the practice of teacher morality. According to Ramli, the manners instilled in a person stem from learning outcomes. In educating, teaching, and guiding students, a teacher should pay attention to etiquette and good manners to avoid harmful deviations (2022:33).

As a social institution, education, as stated by Harris, Jr., represents a behavioral pattern through which knowledge, skills, and concepts are transmitted to individuals through a teaching mechanism (human or otherwise). As a social institution, education aids in imparting social and moral values (1976:44). In this regard, teachers play a central role in carrying out their educational duties, not only as professionals but also as role models with high morals. According to Indriawati et al., teacher ethics uphold professional values and instill good behavior in children (2023:415). The moral and ethical principles upheld by teachers are evident in their interactions with others, especially students, demonstrating their professionalism (Eliza et al., 2022:4270).

The substance of Governor Regulation Number 145 of 2017 is clearly full of social norms. This is evident in the various diction and phrases used and explicitly stated in several provisions of the governor's regulation, including those on politeness, behavior, and refinement (Article 1), behavior and commitment, character and practice of manners (Article 2), practice of manners (Article 3), practical manners, professional manners, caring manners and respectful manners (Article 5), 11 details of practical manners that teachers must carry out (Article 6), 15 details of professional manners that teachers must implement (Article 7), four details of caring manners for teachers (Article 8), and six details of respectful manners for teachers (Article 9). These regulations on teacher manners will serve as a guide for individual teachers in carrying out their professional duties. According to Nurhaliza and Suryatik, a teacher's noble personal values, which prioritize ethics and attitudes that treat and respect others, including fellow teachers and students, will demonstrate their personality (2024:38).

Sociologically, this is crucial to emphasize, in line with Alvin L. Bertrand's definition of social norms as an element of the social system, which constitutes a standard of behavior that is required or justified in certain situations, and can be considered the most critical for understanding and predicting human actions (Abdulsyani, 2007:127). One aspect of these social norms in the world of education is teacher ethics, a moral standard that should serve as the basis for attitudes and behavior in carrying out professional duties. According to Arifin and Umeirsyah,

teacher ethics is a set of moral values and principles that govern behavior in carrying out duties and responsibilities, including when interacting with students (2023:62). Through social interaction within the school institution, teachers can fulfill a crucial role in the social system: the function of maintaining patterns. In the view of Aini and Zaka Hadikusuma Ramadan, the role of teachers in schools is very significant in shaping the character of students who are not only academically intelligent, but also have strong ethical and moral values (2024:338).

Sociologically, the existence of schools as institutions where social values and norms are internalized through the role of teachers is crucial. Gubernur Regulation No. 145 of 2017 clearly states the position and role of schools in achieving the goal of developing teacher morality, which will impact the development of student morality as expected. In the context of social systems, the existence of educational institutions such as schools at various levels and forms, adapting Talcott Parson's opinion, is part of the function of maintaining and/or upholding societal patterns or structures (latent pattern maintenance), as part of societal institutions (Keller, 1995:126). Education aims not only to gain knowledge and understanding of the material, but also aims to shape moral character in children, because science alone is not enough to determine a student's skills if the student lacks character and has good morals (Hafsoh et al., 2022:318). In the context of education in Thailand, Sulastri et al. state that the role of teachers is very important in improving the quality and developing the competencies of elementary school students. Teachers act as effective learning facilitators, creating a positive learning environment, and supporting students' academic, social, and emotional development (2024:6).

Teachers can contribute to students' character development by applying ethical principles in teaching (Haditiah, 2024:228). Teachers must also educate and instill moral values in children by becoming professional teachers. Regarding the role of the teacher in character education, the teacher plays an important role in shaping the character and morals of children (Hafsoh et al., 2021:324). Even more than that, as members of society, whose activities extend beyond the classroom, teachers are also required to serve as role models for their neighbors. In many traditions across various regions, teachers are viewed by the community as figures, often serving as a reference point for decision-making when the community faces problems. One form of teacher involvement, according to Lestari et al., is through social interactions with the community (2024:42). The teacher is able to create conditions that are as comfortable as possible for students, so that in this atmosphere they can learn well. Positive interactions between students, teachers, and students can be a medium for connecting harmonious dialogue so that students can follow everything the teacher teaches them (Zailani, 2023:1247).

In this educational institution, teachers are the primary actors transforming knowledge and also serve as role models for students. According to Ruslan, the teacher's primary role in the learning process, demonstrated by their ethics or behavior as part of their personality, will have a strong influence and pattern on fostering students' behavior and personality (2016:68). Teachers not only teach academic knowledge but also instill character values such as discipline, responsibility, and empathy through various learning activities (Zarkasi, 2024:371). Related to this role as role models, they will always be the center of attention, elevating or degrading the world of education. According to Simangunsong, ethics, manners, or etiquette must be understood, internalized, and practiced by teachers, including those toward students (2023:13). Teachers are individuals to be respected and emulated by students, reflecting good educators who will also foster good perceptions from students (Junaidin, 2023:21).

Community involvement in supporting the implementation of teacher etiquette practices, as stipulated in Article 10 of Gubernatorial Regulation Number 145 of 2017, is also crucial. This encompasses not only their active role in the planning process but also in the implementation and monitoring stages. From a sociological perspective, collaboration between the government and community components constitutes an associative social process, one form of which James D. Thomson calls a coalition (Soekanto, 2009:45). The government cannot work alone in implementing educational programs as mandated by the constitution, so it requires community participation, as a vital instrument that needs to be sustainable and become a culture in society (Pitri, 2017:3, Khaliqa, 2017:24). Community participation is one of the determining factors for the success and progress of educational implementation (Normina, 2016:71).

The discussion of community participation is certainly very broad, at least in line with what Nasikun calls a horizontal social structure in the form of social differentiation, which encompasses differences in religion, ethnicity, race, local culture, and other factors (Narwoko and Bagong Suyatno, 2004:174). Therefore, Article 10 of the gubernatorial regulation should specify in detail the community components expected to participate in supporting this policy on teacher etiquette. For example, the involvement of community organizations or non-governmental organizations working in the fields of education, religion, local culture, and the teaching profession.

CONCLUSION

Teacher etiquette, as part of a teacher's character and part of the dynamics of education, is crucial for the quality of education. State and government policies, including regional governments in South Sulawesi, in the form of Regional Regulation Number 2 of 2016 and Gubernatorial Regulation Number 145 of 2017, are crucial for

achieving educational goals. These regional policies constitute public policies in the field of education, which are crucial for Indonesia's future. Several aspects of public policy are contained within these two regional regulations, as part of the overall public policy framework. Sociologically, the issuance of these two regional policies demonstrates the government's responsiveness to the dynamics of society. As a manifestation of the social system, these two government regulations in South Sulawesi are part of the government's efforts to improve the quality of education. Several aspects of the gubernatorial regulations require refinement.

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